

Volumetric and acoustical behaviour of some amino acids in aqueous magnesium acetate medium

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Abstract : The experimental measurements such as ultrasonic velocity (U), density (ρ) and viscosity (η) were carried out for four amino acids namely, L-alanine, L-leucine, L-valine and L-proline in aqueous magnesium acetate solution under two different molarities (M) (0.5 M and 1 M) at a temperature of 301.15 K. The measured experimental values have been utilised in evaluating the some vital parameters such as adiabatic compressibility (β), molar hydration number (n_H), apparent molar compressibility (ϕ_k), apparent molar volume (ϕ_v), limiting apparent molar compressibility (ϕ_k^0), limiting apparent molar volume (ϕ_v^0) and the constants (S_K, S_V), transfer volume ($\Delta\phi_v^0$), viscosity B -coefficient of Jones-Dole equations were calculated for all the four amino acid systems. Eventually, the present experimental investigation has been critically analysed and discussed in terms of structure-making or structure-breaking effects of these amino acids in the aqueous magnesium acetate mixture.

Keywords : Apparent molar compressibility, apparent molar volume, hydration number, structure-making, structure-breaking.

Introduction

Ultrasonic study on the amino acids with aqueous solution of electrolytes and non-electrolytes provides useful information in understanding the behaviour of intra-molecular and intermolecular associations, complex formation and related structural changes in liquid systems. The investigation of volumetric and thermodynamic properties of amino acids and peptides in aqueous and mixed aqueous solvents has been the area of interest of a number of researchers¹⁻⁶.

Proteins are formed by polymerizing monomers that are known as amino acids, because they contain an amino ($-NH_2$) and a carboxylic acid ($-CO_2H$) functional group. Most of these amino acids differ only in the nature of the R-groups. Amino acids with non-polar substituents are said to be hydrophobic (water hating). Amino acids with polar R-groups that form hydrogen bonds with water are classified as hydrophilic (water loving). The remaining amino acids have substituents that carry either negative or positive charges in aqueous solutions are neutral pH and are therefore strongly hydrophilic.

In the present investigation, at neutral pH, the amino

acids which are taken up for study are L-alanine, L-leucine, L-valine and L-proline are all non-polar R-groups.

The noted effects by the salts on the stability of protein structures and some electrolytes have a tendency to disrupt some of the structural features of proteins, whereas other electrolytes show property to buttress such structures. The study of the thermodynamic ability of the native structure of proteins has proved quite challenging. Salt solutions have large effects on the structure and properties of proteins including their solubility, denaturation, dissociation into subunits. Amino acids are the fundamental structural unit of proteins. But L-amino acids are used in many biological processes in human body like transamination, decarboxylation and metabolism. On the other hand, L-amino acids are also involved in intracellular metabolism and operate specific transport systems of the plasma membrane. Hence, the study of these model compounds (amino acids) in aqueous salt solutions is more significance, in understanding the effects of salts on biomolecules. Various workers have studied the interaction between some amino acids and simple salts^{7,8} which act as stabilizer/destabiliser, but a few studies are avail-

able about the behavior of amino acids in the presence of organic salts^{9,10}. Although various studies of amino acids are available in the presence of electrolytes having univalent cations, but no report has been found in the presence of organic salts having divalent cation.

Moreover, no systematic studies are available on the volumetric, viscometric and ultrasonic studies of amino acids having non-polar side group (chain) in the presence of organic salt solutions. Magnesium acetate find special application in dyeing of ceramic tiles and textile. As a catalyst in polyester film production, in cigarette paper manufacture, in resins and in off-set printing. It is a divalent carbon. Magnesium acetate has been used as organic salt because magnesium found immense importance in biological chemistry. Therefore, in order to understand the behavior of proteins in aqueous salt solutions, the authors has studied the volumetric and ultrasonic studies of some amino acids in aqueous magnesium acetate solution at 301.15 K.

In the present study, it has been reported that the values of density, viscosity and ultrasonic velocity have been measured for the amino acids, L-alanine, L-leucine, L-valine and L-proline in aqueous magnesium acetate solution at 301.15 K. Various parameters like adiabatic compressibility (β), molar hydration number (n_H), apparent molar compressibility (ϕ_K), apparent molar volume (ϕ_V), limiting apparent molar compressibility (ϕ_K^0) and its related constant (S_K), limiting apparent molar volume (ϕ_V^0) and its related constant (S_V), transfer volume ($\Delta\phi_V^0$) and viscosity B -coefficients of Jones-Dole equations have been evaluated and discussed in terms of structure-making and structure-breaking effects of amino acids in the solvent mixture.

Materials and methods :

Analytical reagent grade (AR) and spectroscopic reagent (SR) with minimum assay of 99.9% of four amino acids such as L-alanine, L-leucine, L-valine and L-proline obtained from E. Merck, Germany and Sd fine Chemicals, India, which are used as such without further purification. Water used in the experiments was deionised, distilled and degassed prior to prepare solutions. Aqueous magnesium acetate at two different molarities (M) say, at 0.5 M and at 1 M were prepared by volume and used on the day they were prepared. Solutions of amino

acids in the concentration range of 0.02–0.1 M were made by volume on the molarity (M) concentration scale with a precision of 0.0001 g using an electronic digital balance [Model : Shimadzu AX-200]. The density of liquid mixtures was determined using a specific gravity bottle by relative displacement method with an accuracy of ± 0.01 kg m^{-3} . An Ostwald's viscometer (10 ml capacity) was used for the viscosity measurements with efflux time was determined using a digital chronometer to within ± 0.01 s. An ultrasonic interferometer having the frequency of 3 MHz (Mittal Enterprises, New Delhi, Model : F-81) with overall accuracy of 3 m s^{-1} has been used for velocity measurements. An electronically and digitally operated constant temperature bath (RAGAA Industries, Chennai) has been used to circulate water through the double walled measuring cell made up of steel containing the experimental solution at the desired temperature. The accuracy in the temperature measurement is ± 0.1 K.

Results and discussion

The experimental values of density, viscosity and ultrasonic velocity for different molar composition of the amino acids viz. L-alanine, L-leucine, L-valine and L-proline in aqueous magnesium acetate solution at 301.15 K, which are shown in Table 1. The values of adiabatic compressibility, molar hydration number are reported in Table 2. The apparent molar compressibility, apparent molar volume, limiting apparent molar compressibility of all the systems are presented in Table 3, similarly, the limiting apparent molar volume and their associated constants S_K and S_V , and transfer volume are tabulated in Table 4 and viscosity B -coefficient of Jones-Dole equation are listed in Table 5. Figs. 1–3, show the variations of limiting apparent molar compressibility, limiting apparent molar volume and transfer volume with molar concentration of L-alanine, L-leucine, L-valine and L-proline at a temperature of 301.15 K.

In all the amino acid systems from Table 1, the values of density, viscosity and ultrasonic velocity increases with increase of molar concentration of amino acids as well as the increasing content of the magnesium acetate. The ultrasonic velocity (U) increases with increase in the concentration of the solutes (amino acids) as well as magnesium acetate content. The increasing trend suggests a moderate strong electrolytic nature in which the solute

Table 1. Values of density (ρ), viscosity (η) and ultrasonic velocity (U) of amino acids in aqueous magnesium acetate mixtures at 301.15 K

Molarity (M) (mol dm ⁻³)	Density (ρ) (kg/m ³)			Viscosity (η) ($\times 10^{-3}$ Nsm ⁻²)			Ultrasonic velocity (U) (m/s)		
	0 M	0.5 M	1 M	0 M	0.5 M	1 M	0 M	0.5 M	1 M
	Water + magnesium acetate + L-alanine								
0.00	996.31	1064.34	1102.92	0.8330	1.2784	2.0394	1501.7	1581.47	1656.74
0.02	999.70	1066.72	1104.65	0.8574	1.2941	2.0518	1518.43	1584.35	1658.04
0.04	1000.71	1067.13	1105.76	0.8891	1.2992	2.0910	1519.93	1585.92	1659.60
0.06	1001.27	1068.02	1109.09	0.9011	1.3049	2.1074	1520.37	1586.86	1660.44
0.08	1002.43	1069.09	1109.92	0.9075	1.3123	2.1140	1521.49	1587.57	1661.46
0.10	1003.01	1069.84	1110.76	0.9143	1.3232	2.121	1522.11	1588.21	1663.56
	Water + magnesium acetate + L-leucine								
0.00	996.31	1064.34	1102.92	0.833	1.2784	2.0394	1501.70	1581.47	1656.74
0.02	1000.71	1066.18	1105.90	0.8691	1.2966	2.7050	1516.84	1584.96	1658.10
0.04	1001.23	1067.72	1107.70	0.8803	1.3086	2.1153	1518.21	1585.32	1658.22
0.06	1002.45	1067.81	1108.39	0.8914	1.3087	2.1272	1520.39	1586.16	1658.52
0.08	1003.79	1067.84	1109.46	0.9042	1.3392	2.1503	1521.93	1586.52	1659.0
0.10	1004.32	1067.88	1110.48	0.9181	1.3397	2.1945	1523.12	1587.12	1659.36
	Water + magnesium acetate + L-valine								
0.00	996.31	1064.34	1102.92	0.8330	1.2784	2.0394	1501.7	1581.47	1656.74
0.02	997.45	1067.58	1106.87	0.8604	1.3084	2.0822	1519.73	1585.08	1652.96
0.04	998.31	1068.11	1107.42	0.8715	1.3243	2.1043	1520.65	1585.80	1653.12
0.06	999.61	1068.46	1108.39	0.8843	1.3450	2.1166	1521.37	1586.76	1653.96
0.08	1000.91	1069.79	1109.37	0.8937	1.3518	2.1343	1522.26	1587.84	1654.20
0.10	1001.89	1070.61	1110.34	0.9076	1.3579	2.1415	1523.39	1588.72	1654.56
	Water + magnesium acetate + L-proline								
0.00	996.31	1064.34	1102.92	0.8330	1.2784	2.0394	1501.7	1581.47	1656.74
0.02	998.94	1067.93	1108.39	0.8721	1.3088	2.0640	1519.23	1585.08	1660.35
0.04	999.76	1068.33	1109.92	0.8869	1.3245	2.0879	1520.64	1586.16	1662.96
0.06	1001.03	1069.63	1110.89	0.8981	1.3414	2.1214	1521.97	1586.52	1664.64
0.08	1001.97	1069.72	1111.59	0.9097	1.3466	2.1439	1523.01	1586.64	1666.44
0.10	1003.00	1069.90	1112.42	0.9201	1.3519	2.1560	1524.36	1586.88	1666.80

(amino acids) tend to attract the solvent (magnesium acetate) molecules^{11,12}. Molecular association is thus responsible for the observed increase in ultrasonic velocity in the mixtures. The factors apparently responsible for such behavior may be the presence of interactions caused by the proton transfer reactions of amino acid in water + magnesium acetate mixtures. The increase in ultrasonic velocity in these solutions may be attributed to the cohesion brought about the ionic hydration. It is known that

water + magnesium acetate mixtures of L-alanine, L-leucine, L-valine and L-proline contain in addition to the uncharged molecules $\text{NH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOH}$, an electrically neutral molecule viz. $\text{NH}_3^+\text{CH}_2\text{COO}^-$ dipolarions (Zwitterions).

When the amino acids are dissolved in water + magnesium acetate mixtures, the cations Mg_2^+ and the anions COO^- are formed. The water molecules are attached to the ions strongly to the electrostatic forces, which in-

Table 2. Values of adiabatic compressibility (β) and molar hydration number (n_H) of amino acids in aqueous magnesium acetate mixtures at 301.15 K

Molarity (M) (mol dm ⁻³)	Adiabatic compressibility (β) ($\times 10^{10}$ m ² N ⁻¹)			Molar hydration number ($n_H \times 10^{-1}$)		
	Water + magnesium acetate + L-alanine					
	0 M	0.5 M	1 M	0 M	0.5 M	1 M
0.00	4.4508	3.7566	3.3033	-	-	-
0.02	4.3385	3.7346	3.2929	23.152	20.7192	23.7786
0.04	4.3255	3.7301	3.2834	11.0786	9.8653	11.5682
0.06	4.3206	3.7183	3.2103	7.0705	6.2509	7.3848
0.08	4.3096	3.7101	3.2638	5.0618	4.4541	5.2908
0.10	4.3033	3.7056	3.2531	3.8603	3.3627	4.0203
	Water + magnesium acetate + L-alanine					
	0 M	0.5 M	1 M	0 M	0.5 M	1 M
0.00	4.4508	3.7566	3.3033	-	-	-
0.02	4.3432	3.7338	3.2889	20.3065	18.1071	15.9933
0.04	4.3330	3.7265	3.2832	9.6216	8.5585	7.5330
0.06	4.3154	3.7223	3.2799	6.0882	5.3781	4.6772
0.08	4.3009	3.7205	3.2748	4.262	3.7780	3.2548
0.10	4.2919	3.7175	3.2704	5.2673	2.8298	2.4135
	Water + magnesium acetate + L-valine					
	0 M	0.5 M	1 M	0 M	0.5 M	1 M
0.00	4.4508	3.7566	3.3033	-	-	-
0.02	4.3408	3.7282	3.3065	22.8157	20.5090	18.1389
0.04	4.3318	3.7229	3.3047	10.8841	9.7004	8.5337
0.06	4.3221	3.7172	3.2980	6.9253	6.1292	5.3475
0.08	4.3114	3.7075	3.2941	4.9536	4.3540	3.7698
0.10	4.3008	3.7006	3.2898	3.7715	3.2885	2.8131
	Water + magnesium acetate + L-proline					
	0 M	0.5 M	1 M	0 M	0.5 M	1 M
0.00	4.4508	3.7566	3.3033	-	-	-
0.02	4.3398	3.7269	3.2727	23.1520	20.7192	18.3358
0.04	4.3256	3.7204	3.2579	11.0786	9.8653	8.7033
0.06	4.3126	3.7142	3.2485	7.0705	6.2509	5.4704
0.08	4.3026	3.7134	3.2394	5.0618	4.4541	3.8746
0.10	4.2906	3.7116	3.2356	3.8603	3.3627	2.8975

produce a greater cohesion in the solutions¹³. Thus, the cohesion increases, whenever an increase of amino acid concentration in the solution. The increased association observed in these solutions may also be due to the water structure enhancement brought about by the increase in electrostriction in the presence of magnesium acetate. The electrostriction effect which brings about the shrinkage in volume of solvent caused by the Zwitterionic portion of the amino acids is increased in mixed solvent. Similar

effect was reported by earlier workers^{14,15}.

Density (ρ) is a measure of solvent-solvent and ion-solvent interactions. Increase of density with concentration indicates the increase in solvent-solvent and solute-solvent interactions, whereas the decrease in density indicates the lesser magnitude of solute-solvent and solvent-solvent interactions. Increase in density with concentration is due to the shrinkage in the volume which in turn is due to the presence of solute molecules. In other words,

an increase in density may be interpreted to the structure-maker of the solvent due to the added solute. Similarly, the decrease in density with concentration indicates structure-breaker of the solvent. It may also be true that solvent-solvent interactions bring about a bonding, probably hydrogen bonding between them. So, size of the resultant molecule increases and hence there will be decrease in density.

The Table 2 exhibits the variation of adiabatic compressibility (β) with molar concentration of amino acids. The values of β in all the amino acids systems show a decreasing trend with increasing molar concentration of amino acids as well as magnesium acetate content. The

adiabatic compressibility's values are larger in L-leucine system than those of other amino acid systems. This shows that the molecular association is greater in L-leucine than that of other amino acid systems. Amino acid molecules in the neutral solution exist in dipolar form and then have stronger interaction with the surrounding water molecules. The increasing electrostrictive compression of water around the molecules results in a larger decrease in the compressibility of the solutions.

The interaction between the solute and the water molecules in the solvent is referred to as hydration. From Table 2, it is observed that the values of hydration number n_H are positive in all the systems studied. The values

Table 3. Values of apparent molar compressibility (ϕ_k) and apparent molar volume (ϕ_v) of amino acids in aqueous magnesium acetate mixtures at 301.15 K

Molarity (<i>M</i>) (mol dm ⁻³)	Apparent molar compressibility (ϕ_k) ($\times 10^4$ m ² N ⁻¹)			Apparent molar volume (ϕ_v) (\times m ³ mol ⁻¹)		
	0 <i>M</i>	0.5 <i>M</i>	1 <i>M</i>	0 <i>M</i>	0.5 <i>M</i>	1 <i>M</i>
Water + magnesium acetate + L-alanine						
0.02	63.2526	17.2189	9.4768	168.8745	126.6564	95.4025
0.04	43.7322	10.2937	8.6384	110.0781	74.2377	75.2743
0.06	25.2059	9.6854	10.4368	82.3616	65.2795	113.4169
0.08	20.9123	8.7823	9.1940	76.2177	63.1952	96.5055
0.10	17.6124	7.9464	8.9628	66.7527	58.5386	86.4689
Water + magnesium acetate + L-leucine						
0.02	63.1593	16.5925	14.1867	219.1881	97.9192	164.3350
0.04	34.6873	11.9030	10.4662	123.0873	73.9716	130.8524
0.06	26.9382	8.7883	8.0655	101.9557	61.5543	100.5495
0.08	22.7456	6.8611	7.3119	93.1550	46.5648	90.1637
0.10	19.3248	5.8450	6.7563	79.8044	37.6776	83.3807
Water + magnesium acetate + L-valine						
0.02	57.1224	22.5632	5.2491	56.7896	172.4231	217.8267
0.04	31.7480	13.3124	3.6729	49.8155	100.3140	124.0784
0.06	23.7308	10.1843	4.3959	54.7970	73.0846	100.5495
0.08	19.8464	9.6765	4.3362	57.2878	72.5082	88.9229
0.10	17.3638	8.8504	4.3455	55.5941	66.7341	81.8366
Water + magnesium acetate + L-proline						
0.02	60.9223	23.9990	28.5757	131.0147	191.0490	301.6486
0.04	34.8904	14.2403	20.1822	84.9317	106.1679	193.0109
0.06	26.3520	10.7934	15.9495	78.3763	93.8393	146.5045
0.08	21.5258	8.8061	13.6646	70.4889	71.5768	119.5289
0.10	18.8685	7.9764	11.6963	66.6531	59.1773	104.7774

Table 4. Limiting apparent molar compressibility (ϕ_k^0), limiting apparent molar volume (ϕ_v^0), and their constants S_K and S_V of amino acids

Amino acids	Molarity (<i>M</i>) (mol dm ⁻³)	Limiting apparent	Constant	Limiting apparent	Constant
		molar compressibility (ϕ_k^0) ($\times 10^{-8} \text{ m}^2 \text{ N}^{-1}$)	(S_K) ($\times 10^{-8} \text{ N}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	molar volume (ϕ_v^0) ($\times \text{m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	(S_V) ($\text{N}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$)
L-Alanine	0	-68.28	143.45	-201.713	-423.468
	0.5	-21.58	45.34	-151.162	325.972
	1	-18.68	39.25	-186.827	392.494
L-Leucine	0	-66.74	140.21	-246.876	518.647
	0.5	-19.99	42.01	-127.074	266.964
	1	-18.71	39.31	-227.712	478.387
L-Valine	0	-59.92	125.89	-109.713	230.490
	0.5	-27.43	57.63	-194.025	407.616
	1	-8.799	18.48	-245.285	515.305
L-Proline	0	-65.02	136.60	-119.263	250.553
	0.5	-26.06	54.75	-155.462	318.198
	1	-36.02	75.68	-346.188	727.285

Table 5. Values of *A* and *B* parameters of Jones-Dole equation of amino acids

Amino acids	<i>A</i> ($\times \text{dm}^{-3/2} \text{ m}^{-1/2}$)			<i>B</i> ($\times \text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)		
	Temperature (301.15 K)					
	0 <i>M</i>	0.5 <i>M</i>	1 <i>M</i>	0 <i>M</i>	0.5 <i>M</i>	1 <i>M</i>
L-Alanine	3.2658	0.06376	0.0037	-12.4595	0.11645	0.4564
L-Leucine	0.3029	0.0442	0.0469	-0.0273	0.3480	0.5743
L-Valine	0.1919	-0.4851	0.1508	0.2488	0.0269	0.0259
L-Proline	0.3504	0.1676	-0.0027	-0.1019	0.04611	0.4257

Fig. 1. Variation of limiting apparent molar compressibility (ϕ_k^0) with molarity: (◆) 0.0 *M*, (■) 0.5 *M*, (▲) 1.0 *M*.

Fig. 2. Variation of limiting apparent molar volume (ϕ_v^0) with molarity: (◆) 0.0 *M*, (■) 0.5 *M*, (▲) 1.0 *M*.

n_H are found to be decreased with increase in molarity of the amino acids as well as content of magnesium acetate. However, it shows a reverse trend is observed in L-alanine system. The possession of positive values of n_H indicate an appreciable solvation of solutes. This is an added

support for the structure promoting nature of solutes as well as the presence of dipolar interaction between the solute and water molecules. This also suggests that compressibility of the solution will be less than that of the solvent. As a result solutes will gain mobility and have

Fig. 3. Variation of transfer volume ($\Delta\phi_v^0$) with molarity : (♦) 0.0 M, (■) 0.5 M, (▲) 1.0 M.

more probability of contacting solvent molecules. This may enhance the interaction between solute and solvent molecules. Further in the present study, the decreasing values of n_H which indicate the increase in solute-cosolute interaction. The decreasing behavior of n_H shows that magnesium acetate has a hydration effect in the amino acids.

The values of apparent molar compressibility (ϕ_K) and apparent molar volume (ϕ_v) are tabulated in Table 3. The following observations have been made on apparent molar compressibility (ϕ_K) and apparent molar volume (ϕ_v) of L-alanine, L-leucine, L-valine and L-proline in aqueous magnesium acetate solution at 301.15 K.

(i) The values of the (ϕ_K) and (ϕ_v) are all negative over the entire range molarity of amino acids.

(ii) The values of ϕ_K are increasing with increasing molarity of the amino acids.

(iii) However, the values of ϕ_K decrease with increase in content of magnesium acetate in all the three amino acids systems, whereas a reverse trend is observed in L-valine system.

(iv) Similarly, the ϕ_v values also increase with increasing molarity of amino acids in all the four systems and decrease with the increase in content of the magnesium acetate.

(v) The maximum value of ϕ_K and ϕ_v obtained for L-leucine system comparing all the other three amino acids systems, indicating that a strong molecular association is found in L-leucine system.

(vi) Such a maximum values of apparent molar compressibility (ϕ_K) as well as apparent molar volume (ϕ_v) are obtained for L-leucine system, which suggests

electrostriction and hydrophilic interactions occurring in these systems, thereby indicating the presence of solute-solvent interactions.

(vii) From the magnitudes of (ϕ_K) and (ϕ_v), the molecular association between the four systems of amino acids are of the order : L-leucine > L-alanine > L-proline > L-valine.

All the observations clearly suggest that the negative values of ϕ_K and ϕ_v in all systems indicate the presence of ion-solvent interactions too. Further, the negative values of (ϕ_K) indicate electrostrictive solvation of ions¹⁶. The observed increasing behavior of ϕ_v suggest the existence of strong solute-solvent interaction in all the systems studied. The negative values of (ϕ_K) indicate ionic, dipolar and hydrophilic interactions occurring in these systems. Since more number of water molecules are available at lower concentration of magnesium acetate, the chances for the penetration of solute molecules into the solvent molecules is highly favored. The decreasing values of (ϕ_K) in the concerned systems reveal that weakening of ion-solvent interactions existing in these mixtures. From the magnitude of ϕ_K and ϕ_v , it can be concluded that a strong molecular interaction is found in L-leucine than other three amino acids and suggesting that the L-leucine is a more effective structure-maker than any other amino acids in the solvent mixture.

The limiting apparent molar compressibility (ϕ_K^0) values provide information regarding the ion-solvent interactions and its related constant (S_K) of the ion-ion interactions in the solution, which are tabulated in Table 4.

The ϕ_K^0 values are negative in all the systems and increase with increase of magnesium acetate content, except in L-proline system, in which a reverse trend is noticed. Appreciable negative values of ϕ_K^0 for all the systems which suggest our earlier view that the existence of ion-solvent interactions. The large values of ϕ_K^0 is noticed in L-leucine system than other amino acid systems.

The values of S_K exhibit positive values and decrease with increase of magnesium acetate content in all the three amino acid systems and however, it finds a reverse trend in L-proline system. The positive values of S_K indicate the strengthening of ion-ion interactions and suggest the structure-making effect of the amino acids. It is well known that solutes causing electrostriction leading to decrease in

the compressibility of the solution. This is reflected in the negative values of ϕ_k of amino acids in aqueous magnesium acetate solution.

The perusal of Table 4 represents the values of limiting apparent molar volume ϕ_v^0 which exhibit negative values in all the four systems and decrease with increase in content of magnesium acetate in all the systems studied. This enhances/reduces the electrostriction of water molecules. Decrease of ϕ_v^0 is due to enhancement in electrostriction at the terminal groups of amino acids, which decreases the interaction between these polar ends and ions. The decrease of ϕ_v^0 values in magnesium acetate solution may be attributed to hydrophobicity/polar character of the side chains of the amino acids. Hence, such a decreasing values of ϕ_v^0 in magnesium acetate solution clearly indicate the weakening of the ion-solvent interaction. It is evident from the Table 4 that the values of S_V are positive in all the four amino acid systems and increase with increase of magnesium acetate content in the mixture. Such a possession of positive values of S_V clearly indicates the presence of strong ion-ion interactions in the solution.

In the present amino acid systems, it may be presumed that the interactions may be taking place as,

(i) Ion-dipolar/hydrophilic group interactions between the ions of magnesium acetate (Mg^{2+} , CH_3COO^-) and (NH_3^+ , COO^-), ($-OH$) group of amino acids¹².

(ii) Ion-hydrophilic group interaction between the ions of magnesium acetate and polar parts of amino acids.

(iii) Hydrophilic-ionic interaction between the Mg^{2+} , COO^- group of magnesium acetate and Zwitterionic centres of the amino acids.

(iv) Hydrophilic-hydrophobic interaction between the Mg^{2+} , COO^- group of magnesium acetate molecules and OH of the amino acids.

The transfer volume ($\Delta\phi_v^0$) which can be explained on the basis of co-sphere overlap model¹⁷ in terms of solute-co-solute interactions. According to this model, the positive values are suggesting the hydrophilic-ionic group interactions, whereas the negative values are suggesting the hydrophobic-ionic group interactions. In the present study (from Fig. 3), the positive $\Delta\phi_v^0$ values were observed for L-alanine and L-leucine system, and the nega-

tive $\Delta\phi_v^0$ values observed for L-valine and L-proline systems suggesting that hydrophilic/ionic group of interactions are present in the former systems and ionic-hydrophobic group of interactions are dominating in the latter systems.

Viscosity is an important parameter in understanding the structure as well as molecular interactions occurring in the solutions. Viscosity variation is attributed to the structural changes. The structural changes influence the viscosity to a certain extent as compared to density and compressibility. From Table 5, it is observed that the values of viscosity increases with increase in solute concentration in all the systems. This increasing trend indicates the existence of molecular interaction occurring in these systems. In order to shed more light on this, the role of viscosity B -coefficient has also been obtained. From Table 5, it is observed that the values of A are almost positive and B -coefficients are positive in all systems. Since A is a measure of ionic interaction¹⁸ it is evident that there is a strong ion-ion interactions present in the liquid mixtures. The B -coefficient which is known for measure of order or disorder introduced by the solute in the solvent. It is also a measure of solute-solvent interaction. The behaviour of B -coefficient in all the amino acids suggests the existence of strong solute-solvent interaction. The magnitude of B -values is higher in L-leucine which clearly confirms the amino acid L-leucine is acting as a effective structure-maker in aqueous magnesium acetate solution. Similar trends of interaction studies studied for other amino acids in aqueous sodium acetate solution have been reported earlier¹² which supports the present investigation. From the magnitude of B -coefficient, it can be concluded that the molecular interaction between the amino acids is of the order : L-leucine > L-alanine > L-proline > L-valine.

The above conclusion is an excellent earlier agreement with that drawn from ϕ_k and ϕ_v data.

Conclusion :

From the present investigation, it may be concluded that intermolecular interaction of electrostriction and hydrophilic nature exist in the systems studied. The existence of solute-co-solute or solute-solvent interactions resulting in attractive forces which promote the structure-making tendency, while ion-ion or solute-solute interaction resulting dipole-dipole, dipole-induced dipole and

electrostrictive forces enhance the structure-breaking properties of amino acids. By analysing critically all the evaluated parameters, it is very obvious that L-leucine is a strong structure-maker in aqueous magnesium acetate solution over the other three amino acids. However, a weak ion-solvent interaction is noticed in the present system of mixtures. The transfer volume studies dealing about the solute-co-solute molecules predict that hydrophilic-ionic group interactions are existing in L-alanine and L-leucine systems and hydrophobic-ionic group of interactions are dominating in L-valine and L-proline systems.

In the present study, the molecular interaction follows the order : L-leucine > L-alanine > L-proline > L-valine.

References

1. M. M. Duke, Andrew W. Hakin, Robert M. McKay and Kathryn E. Preuss, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1994, **72**, 1489.
2. A. W. Hakin, Michelle M. Dukem, Sheri A. Klassen, Roert M. McKay and Kathryn E. Preuss, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1994, **72**, 362.
3. T. V. Chalikian, Armen, P. Saravazyan, Theodor Funck and Kenneth J. Breslauer, *Biopolymers*, 1994, **34**, 5541.
4. G. R. Hedwig and H. Hoiland, *J. Chem. Thermodyn.*, 1991, **23**, 1029.
5. J. L. Marty, Andrew W. Hakin, Michelle M. Duke and Kathryn E. Preuss, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1994, **90**, 2027.
6. S. Thirumaran and AN. Kannappan, *Global Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 2009, **2**, 160.
7. A. Kumar and R. Badrayani, *J. Chem. Thermodyn.*, 2003, **35**, 897.
8. T. S. Banipal, Damanjit Kaura, P. K. Banipal and Gagandeep Singha, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2004, **43**, 1156.
9. Z. Yan, J. Wnag and L. Jinsuo, *J. Chem. Engg. Data*, 2001, **46**, 217.
10. J. Wang, Y. Zhenning and L. Jinsuo, *J. Chem. Thermodyn.*, 2004, **36**, 281.
11. Zhenning Yan, Jianji Wang and Jinsoo Lu, *J. Chem. Engg. Data*, 2001, **46**, 217.
12. T. S. Banipal, Damanjit Kaura, P. K. Banipal and Gagandeep Singha, *J. Chem. Thermodyn.*, 2007, **39**, 371.
13. D. Ragouramane and A. S. Rao, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1998, **37**, 659.
14. R. Palani and S. Saravanan, *Research Journal of Physics*, 2008, **2**, 13.
15. S. Thirumaran and K. Job Sabu, *Indian J. Pure Appl. Phys.*, 2009, **47**, 87.
16. A. Dhanalakshmi and E. Jasmine Vasantharan, *J. Pure Appl. Ultrason.*, 1992, **21**, 79.
17. R. Palani and S. Balakrishnan, *Archiv. Phys. Rev.*, 2010, **1**, 1.
18. H. Falkenhagen and E. L. Vernan, *Z. Phys.*, 1933, **33**, 111.

